

CURRENT FINTECH TRENDS

Tolibjonov KHurshidbek

Student of Kokand University

Yetmishboev Shakhzodbek

Student of the Fergana branch of the

TATU

Azamov Shoxruxmirzo

Student of the Fergana branch

of the TATU

Annotation: In this article, you can learn about the changes that fintech startups have made in the banking industry. It is no exaggeration to say that the emergence of Fintech caused new problems for many banks, and this eventually led to a dead end. But Fintech's methods in the banking industry have made things a little easier. You can see all the information about them throughout the article.

Keywords: Fintech, open banking, API, financial institutions, DBF, platform wrapping.

Numerous fintech trends will shape the emerging banking landscape over the next few years. Fintech startups build their businesses on banking application software interfaces (APIs); cooperating with banks, which allows them to act as ersatz banks; differentiate themselves by offering an ever-expanding basket of retail banking products and services; and change their way of working from being a separator of banking services to an aggregator of those services. Major social media-focused platforms want to build or expand their fintech companies.

Finally, large financial institutions want to develop their fintech capabilities so that they can compete with small but fast fintech startups and technologically heavyweights. New banks focused on digital assets are starting to emerge.

The emergence of open banking legislation initiatives will significantly facilitate these changes. Open banking is a reality in Europe, and it is slowly gaining

ground in the rest of the world. Based on the new legislation, fintech companies can create plugins and game APIs that use open financial data. Whereas in the past each bank stored the financial information of its customers, now the consumer financial information stored by different financial institutions can be retrieved through a single API. The availability of this data will create new competition for practitioners by allowing fintech companies to use such APIs as building blocks for their emerging business models.

Thanks to new developments in the introduction of information technology and mobile telecommunications, we are seeing the potential growth of an unstoppable third wave of innovation in the banking sector. We list the main features, advantages and strategic imperatives of the future digital banking (DBF).

To understand the opportunity to announce this third wave, we will explore the first two waves of digital innovation in the banking industry.

When considering platform competition in the banking industry, we need to consider competitors that may emerge in different markets. Existing platforms that “have similar user bases and use similar components” may be well-known contenders. In such a scenario, “platform wrapping” strategies can be applied to enter a new market by expanding the functionality of its platform to take advantage of the overall relationships and interactions of users.

We currently follow a banking strategy platform on the example of major technology platforms, such as Facebook and Google, moving towards a banking domain using user bases, trusted brands and existing features to offer banking services. Some of these platforms already operate on the edge of the financial services sector. For example, Amazon already runs a payment service and lending business to SMEs that sell products on its website, which enhances network interaction and leads to business. Facebook recently set up peer-to-peer payments between Messenger accounts in the United States, then obtained an electronic money license in the Republic of Ireland to pave the way for Messenger payments in Europe.

The disruption in banking by large technology platforms is exacerbated by fintech startups who are frustrated with the closed strategies of traditional banks, which may see global technology firms as the main platform for disseminating their innovative services. Banks will need to learn how to compete with these existing firms and operate on a platform and ecosystem basis to remain competitive. Such competition can lead to a multi-platform stack, where multiple platforms sit on top of each other (vertical stacking) to study the inefficiencies in an existing banking system and gain value from customers. While this is expected to bring some benefits to customers in the medium term, it will restructure the value chain of banking services and redistribute market share and profits in the sector. Depending on the market response, this may affect banks' pricing strategies and customer rewards.

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